

A low-cost methodology based on artificial intelligence for contamination detection in microalgae production systems

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Abstract

This work presents the development of a neural network for the classification of microalgae genera that allows the detection of contamination in the analysed sample by focusing on the output of the softmax layer. The data necessary to perform the classification are obtained by means of a spectral sweep in the 300-750 nm range, to which a baseline correction is applied in order to obtain a cleaner spectrum without unwanted fluctuations, facilitating the identification and analysis of the relevant spectral components. The developed model has been trained based on the data obtained from pure samples of 4 different genera of microalgae, *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Synechococcus* and *Scenedesmus*, obtaining as a result a network that allows classification correctly and with high accuracy rate the genera of the pure samples introduced. The network was initially validated with new samples obtained in the laboratory after training obtaining a macro F1 score of 98.64%. Afterwards, the resulting model was tested in three different photobioreactors, two race-way reactors, and one tubular reactor, to demonstrate the capabilities of the proposed methodology for contamination detection purposes. This makes it possible to monitor cultures without the need to invest in new acquisition devices or the time of qualified operators for technical monitoring. Moreover, this solution highly contributes to the maintenance of the reactor operation detecting possible contamination in advance.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Classification, Convolutional networks,

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Microalgae are photosynthetic microorganisms that have attracted con-
3 siderable interest in recent years due to their potential to address a variety of
4 environmental and food challenges. Such single-celled microorganisms have
5 the ability to reproduce and grow rapidly in a wide variety of environments
6 (Tapie and Bernard, 1988), making them a valuable source of sustainable
7 solutions to currently pressing environmental problems, such as wastewater
8 treatment (Nordio et al., 2022). Microalgae offer a promising solution in
9 this field. These organisms can remove pollutants and unwanted nutrients
10 present in wastewater through their absorption and assimilation capacity. In
11 addition, during their growth, microalgae convert carbon dioxide (CO_2) into
12 biomass, which contributes to mitigate climate change by reducing green-
13 house gas emissions. Microalgae also have enormous potential in the field of
14 food and nutrition. They are rich in proteins, lipids, vitamins, and essential
15 minerals, making them a valuable source of nutrients (Spolaore et al., 2006).
16 However, some microalgae species contain bioactive compounds with antiox-
17 idant properties, making them also ideal for the production of functional
18 foods and nutritional supplements. Microalgae production can be carried
19 out using a variety of systems, including closed and open photobioreactors.
20 Closed photobioreactors offer greater control over culture conditions, which
21 can result in increased microalgae productivity and quality. On the other
22 hand, open photobioreactors, such as ponds and lagoons, are more economi-
23 cal and suitable for large-scale production (Banerjee and Ramaswamy, 2017;
24 Villalobos et al., 2019). However, one of the challenges of open ponds is
25 the contamination of the culture. In an open environment, there is the risk
26 that other undesirable genera of microalgae may colonise and compete with
27 the species of interest. Contamination can have a significant impact on the
28 quality and productivity of a culture, affecting both the expected results
29 and the overall yield. It is therefore crucial to implement strict control and
30 continuous monitoring of the culture environment to mitigate this problem.
31 Facilitating the detection of contamination is especially important, as iden-
32 tifying it in the early stages can help to minimise its growth and prevent
33 it from becoming the dominant strain in the culture. Since culture opti-
34 mization depends on the control of strain-specific factors in the reactors, it

35 is essential to maintain the desired strain at as high a ratio as possible to
36 maximize yield and efficiency (Nordio et al., 2023). Complete elimination of
37 contamination, especially in open reactors, is often a challenge (Wang et al.,
38 2013); however, reducing contamination to minimal levels is feasible by mon-
39 itoring the culture as part of the daily routine operation. Thus, improved
40 proactive monitoring and detection measures are important challenges in the
41 operation of such cultures.

42
43 Currently, this process is carried out by manual analysis of samples under
44 the visual inspection of an expert capable of discerning the morphological dif-
45 ferences between genera using an optical microscope (Roy et al., 2022), which
46 requires highly skilled workers. To facilitate this process, the use of FlowCam
47 for the acquisition of microalgae images and neural networks to classify them
48 has been studied in Otálora Berenguel et al. (2021); Otálora et al. (2023).
49 This has made it possible to replicate the process performed in the labora-
50 tory, but in a faster and more accurate way, although with the disadvantage
51 that the use of FlowCam requires a high investment. Following this path,
52 Salmi et al. (2022) gives a complete solution, as it allows one to classify gen-
53 res, even mixtures, and concentration at the same time, making use of neural
54 networks as well. For this, they make use of a Specim IQ spectral imager to
55 obtain spectral images in the 420-850 nm range with 7 nm increments and a
56 1-dimensional convolutional neural network that outputs the concentration
57 of the five genres used in the training, allowing classification and quantifi-
58 cation at the same time. Despite the high accuracy of these methods and
59 those based on Flowcam images, these solutions require a high economic in-
60 vestment to acquire the different needed devices. Furthermore, the works
61 mentioned only address the task of classification, but do not deal with the
62 problem of detecting culture contamination. In Çağatay Işil et al. (2021),
63 a flow cytometer, which is expensive and requires specialized personnel, is
64 used to classify microalgae and the possibilities of performing contamination
65 detection are discussed. The same happens in in Giakoumoglou et al. (2024),
66 where an AI-based flow cytometer is created with the help of images obtained
67 by optical microscopy.

68
69 In this work, we aim to develop an alternative and more economical ap-
70 proach in comparison to traditional methods for the classification of mi-
71 croalgal genera. Traditional methods, such as FlowCam, flow cytometry and
72 Specim IQ spectral imaging, involve high costs and require specialised exper-

73 tise, limiting their accessibility and practicality for many laboratories. The
74 equipment and maintenance costs associated with these techniques, together
75 with the need for trained personnel to operate complex software and interpret
76 the data, pose significant barriers to their widespread adoption. In contrast,
77 the approach we propose aims to mitigate these challenges by offering a more
78 cost-effective and user-friendly alternative that allows greater accessibility to
79 microalgae classification in a variety of industrial and research environments.
80 For this purpose, an optical spectrometer was used to obtain spectral sweep
81 in the 350 - 750 nm range with a step of 0.5 nm. This type of instrument is
82 commonly used in laboratories for nutrient analysis in cultures, so its avail-
83 ability is high in microalgae culture plants. Therefore, a neural network was
84 developed based on 1D convolutional layers, which are particularly suitable
85 for working with sequential data, as in this case, where each sample is a spec-
86 trum. And following deep learning concepts to process the spectral data, the
87 classification of the microalgae genera was performed, as well as allowing to
88 exploit the raw output of the softmax layer to detect possible contamination
89 of the sample.

90
91 The neural network was trained using a previously labelled dataset, which
92 included spectra of different microalgae genres. During training, the network
93 learnt to identify specific patterns and features in the spectra that allowed
94 it to distinguish between the different genres. Once trained, it was able to
95 classify new microalgae samples on the basis of their spectra. The resulting
96 model trained with lab samples was then tested in three different actual pho-
97 tobioreactors under indoor and outdoor conditions to validate the proposed
98 approach. The results provided high accuracy and efficiency for all the tests
99 performed, presenting this solution as a suitable methodology for contamina-
100 tion detection in microalgae-based photobioreactors. Note that digital images
101 of a microscope were used to confirm the results of the proposed model.

102 **2. Materials and methods**

103 The purpose of this section is to detail the tools used during the devel-
104 opment of this work.

105 *2.1. Microalgae genres*

106 For the training of the net, four species available at the IFAPA center (La
107 Cañada) were used, one for each genus to be classified, with different mor-

108 phologies: *Spirulina platensis*, *Chlorella Vulgaris*, *Synechococcus elongatus*
109 and *Scenedesmus Almeriensis* cultivated in laboratory. Each of these species
110 has particular characteristics and is used in various applications because of
111 its biological and chemical properties.

112 The genus of *Spirulina* is widely known for its high protein, vitamin,
113 and mineral content. This microalgae has traditionally been used as a di-
114 etary supplement due to its nutritional value and health benefits. Its an-
115 tioxidant, immunomodulatory, and antimicrobial properties also make it an
116 object of interest in the food and pharmaceutical industry (Kumar et al.,
117 2022). *Chlorella* is recognised for its high lipid-accumulating capacity and
118 its polyunsaturated fatty acid content. In addition, possible beneficial health
119 effects such as lowering cholesterol levels and improving the immune system
120 are being investigated (Barghchi et al., 2023). *Synechococcus* is a genus val-
121 ued for its effective mechanism of adaptation to changes in salinity and light
122 intensity (Kim et al., 2018). *Scenedesmus* has aroused interest in the pro-
123 duction of biodiesel and the treatment of wastewater to reduce its nitrogen
124 and phosphorus content (Nordio et al., 2022; Park et al., 2011).

125 2.2. Photobioreactors

126 During the validation of the tool, samples were taken from three dif-
127 ferent photobioreactors located at the IFAPA Research Centre (La Cañada,
128 Almería). Two of them are open raceway reactors, and one is a closed tubular
129 reactor.

130 The first raceway (Figure 1) is installed inside a building and is an inter-
131 mediate step between an industrial reactor and a laboratory-scale system. It
132 has a total surface of 0.56 m² and is composed of two 1.4 m straight channels
133 connected by a 0.2 m wide U-shaped curve. The culture height is 0.1 m,
134 which gives a culture volume of 50 litres. The reactor is illuminated with
135 artificial light using 16 led tubes (OSRAM ST5HO80) of 37W, for each reac-
136 tor, that simulate the sunlight cycle. Culture conditions are monitored using
137 a pH and temperature probe (Crison 5334) and a dissolved oxygen probe
138 (Mettler Toledo inPro6050). Using the above measures, the dissolved oxy-
139 gen is controlled by injecting air to keep it below saturation 200%, and the
140 pH is controlled by injecting CO₂ to keep it at 8. The culture temperature
141 is controlled by a stainless steel heat exchanger inserted in one of the reactor
142 channels.

143 The other raceway (Figure 2) is installed inside a greenhouse and has
144 the characteristics of an industrial indoor. It has a surface of 80 m² and is

Figure 1: $0.56m^2$ Raceway reactor

145 composed of two 40 m straight channels connected by a 1 m wide U-shaped
146 curve that, operated at 15 centimetres, provides a culture volume of 12000
147 litres. Carbonation is performed in a sump, which dimensions are 1.0m depth,
148 0.65m length, and 1.0m width. In this sump, CO_2 gas or air can be injected
149 through three plate membrane diffusers at the bottom of the sump (AFD 270,
150 EcoTec). Raceway channels are made of low-density polyethylene of 3mm
151 thickness, while curves and sump are made of high-density polyethylene of
152 3mm thickness.

Figure 2: $80m^2$ Raceway reactor

153 The tubular reactor (Figure 3) is also installed inside a greenhouse, and
154 this one consists of solar light receivers and a bubble column. The light
155 receivers consist of tubes of 19 m in length and 0.09 m in diameter, united in
156 a loop configuration, with a total horizontal length of 400 m and a working

157 volume of 2.6 m². The bubble column has a height of 3.5 m and a diameter
158 of 0.5 m, with a work volume of 0.45 m³. This column was used to remove
159 the gases accumulated in the system as oxigen and control the pH injecting
160 CO₂.

Figure 3: 2400L tubular reactor

161 2.3. Spectrophotometer

162 In the present study, spectral sweeps were carried out using a Genesys
163 10S UV-VIS spectrophotometer (Figure 4a) located at the laboratory of the
164 IFAPA centre (La Cañada), located near the University of Almeria. The
165 sweeps were performed in a wavelength range from 350 to 750 nm with 0.5
166 nm step. This wavelength range was finally selected to cover both the ul-
167 traviolet A and visible spectra, thus allowing the characterisation of samples
168 in this wide wavelength range. Spectral scans were performed using quartz
169 cuvettes to allow the passage of UVA light and maintain the scan with an
170 absorbance between 0.1 and 1, diluting in the case of exceeding it. This
171 methodology allowed for a complete absorption profile of the samples in the
172 range of interest, providing detailed information on the optical properties of
173 the analysed compounds. Each sample introduced into the spectrometer was
174 subjected to three consecutive scans, with shaking between each scan. This
175 procedure was implemented to obtain replicates for comparison purposes and
176 to exclude any scans displaying visible anomalies.

177 *2.4. Optical Microscope*

178 During the validation stage in the reactors of the IFAPA Research Centre,
179 optical inspections of the culture were carried out using an optical microscope
180 to check the state of the culture and to verify if there was any type of con-
181 tamination. The optical microscope used, as well as the spectrophotometer,
182 is located in the laboratory of the research centre and is a Leica DM500
183 microscope (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Spectrophotometer and optical microscope used on IFAPA Lab

184 *2.5. Machine learning techniques*

185 Machine learning is a branch of artificial intelligence that enables systems
186 to learn from data, identify patterns, and make decisions with minimal hu-
187 man intervention. This field encompasses various techniques and algorithms
188 that allow computers to improve their performance on tasks through experi-
189 ence. Among the primary applications of machine learning are classification
190 and regression tasks. In classification, the objective is to categorize data into
191 predefined labels or classes based on input features. Regression, on the other
192 hand, aims to predict continuous values or quantities, identifying trends and
193 relationships within the data to make accurate predictions.

194 In this work, classification techniques will be used due to the nature
195 of the data and objectives, which require assigning specific categories from
196 observed characteristics. Classification techniques cover a variety of methods,
197 ranging from classical algorithms to advanced approaches. Among the most
198 commonly used techniques are Support Vector Machines (SVM), XGBoost,
199 Random Forest and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), each suitable
200 for different types of problems and data structures (Syed et al., 2024). The
201 choice of the ideal classification technique depends largely on factors such
202 as the type of data, the complexity of the problem, and the availability of
203 computational resources, as each method has particular strengths in terms
204 of accuracy, interpretability, and efficiency.

205 2.6. Neural networks

206 This section describes the different types of layers used in the construc-
207 tion of the neural network developed during this work.

208

209 2.6.1. 1D Convolutional layers

210 1D convolutional neural networks (1D CNNs) are a variant of convolu-
211 tional neural networks designed specifically to process one-dimensional data,
212 such as text sequences (Kim, 2014), time series or audio signals (Abdoli et al.,
213 2019). These networks are very effective in the classification, pattern detec-
214 tion, and feature extraction tasks in sequential data (Ko et al., 2022).

215

216 The operation of 1D convolutional neural networks is based on the appli-
217 cation of convolutional filters along one dimension of the input data, usually
218 the temporal dimension. These filters slide over the input sequence, comput-
219 ing different weighted sums of the input values. As the filter slides, local fea-
220 tures are generated that capture specific patterns in the sequence, as shown
221 in Figure 5.

Figure 5: 1D Convolutional filter

222 *2.6.2. BatchNormalisation layers*

223 Batch normalisation is a technique used in deep neural networks to nor-
224 malise activations in a layer by calculating the mean and variance of the
225 current batch. The activations are then normalised to have a mean of zero
226 and a variance of one. This stabilises training, speeds up convergence, and
227 reduces the risk of overfitting (Bjorck et al., 2018).

228 *2.6.3. MaxPooling layers*

229 Once the features have been extracted using convolutional layers, *pool-*
230 *ing* layers are used to reduce the dimensionality and summarise the relevant
231 information. The *pooling* in 1D CNN networks is generally performed by
232 the *max pooling* operation, which selects the maximum value in each *pooling*
233 window.

234
235 *MaxPooling* process is performed by sliding windows that move across
236 the input. For each window position, the maximum value within is selected
237 and that value is taken as the output in the new representation. In this way,
238 the input features are subsampled, reducing their size.

240 *2.6.4. Dropout layers*

241 *Dropout* layer is used in neural networks to avoid overfitting during train-
242 ing. It works by randomly disconnecting a fraction of the neurons in the layer
243 during each training iteration. This means that during the backpropagation
244 process, disconnected neurons do not contribute to weight adjustments, re-
245 ducing the interdependence between neurons, and promotes a more robust
246 and generalised representation of the data. During the inference or evalua-
247 tion phase, the dropout is not applied and all neurons are active to generate
248 consistent predictions (Srivastava et al., 2014).

249
250 In 1D convolutional networks, it is more useful to use *SpatialDropout*
251 (Tompson et al., 2015) because instead of randomly disconnecting neurons,
252 it randomly disconnects a fraction of the complete feature maps (filters ap-
253 plied by the convolutional layer) during each training iteration. This means,
254 analogously to conventional *Dropout*, that all the features corresponding to
255 that channel are not used for weight adjustments during the backpropagation
256 process.

257 2.6.5. Dense layers

258 Dense layers, also known as fully connected layers, are a fundamental
259 component of artificial neural networks. When data is processed through
260 a dense layer, each neuron performs two main operations: a linear combi-
261 nation and a nonlinear activation function. Linear combination consists of
262 multiplying each input by its corresponding weight and then adding a bias.
263 This stage captures weighted relationships between inputs. The nonlinear
264 activation function introduces the ability to capture more complex patterns
265 and features by introducing nonlinearity into the process. This allows cap-
266 turing complex patterns in the data as they pass through the neural network.

267
268 In this work, two first dense layers with an activation function *ReLU* are
269 used, in charge of interpreting the features extracted by the convolutional
270 filters, and finally, a final dense layer with activation function *softmax* is
271 included to obtain a probability distribution, thus allowing one to approach
272 a multiclass classification problem. This process ensures that the output
273 values are in the range 0 to 1 and that the sum of all items equals 1, allowing
274 the results to be interpreted as probabilities.

275 3. Results

276 This section presents first the model development using lab data for cali-
277 bration and validation purposes. Afterwards, the resulting neural network is
278 evaluated using three different actual reactors for indoor and outdoor condi-
279 tions.

280 3.1. Neural network development

281 As a first step in the development of the network, a wide set of spec-
282 tral sweeps was performed on the different species mentioned in the previous
283 section. The Genesys 10S UV-VIS spectrophotometer was used to perform
284 these sweeps in the wavelength range from 350 to 750 nm, using a quartz
285 cuvette because of its transparency in the UVA range, thus allowing accurate
286 measurements to be obtained in all selected spectra. In addition, appropri-
287 ate dilutions of the samples were performed following the Lambert-Beer law,
288 which states that the absorbance is proportional to the concentration of the
289 sample and the optical path length. These dilutions were necessary to keep
290 the readings within the linear range of the Lambert-Beer law, thus avoiding
291 signal saturation and ensuring a linear relationship between absorbance and

292 concentration (Mayerhöfer et al., 2020). In this way, accurate and reliable
293 quantitative results were obtained in order to generate a robust data set cov-
294 ering different stages of growth in the culture.

295

296 In order to create a homogeneous data set for the training and validation
297 of the neural network, a *DataFrame* was generated, using the *Python* library
298 *Pandas* (McKinney, 2010), in which the genus and absorbance analysed along
299 all spectral sweep length waves were introduced as a row. Figure 6 shows
300 the 661 sweeps, including the blank sweeps used for the calibration of the
301 spectrophotometer. It is possible to discern a few patterns in some samples,
302 obviating the blank sweeps, which are clearly distinguishable because of their
303 practically static value. However, it is impossible to determine the different
304 sweeps for the different microalgae genus. It is necessary to label each sweep
305 to the corresponding genus to realise that similar patterns are obtained, as
306 shown in Figure 7. Therefore, this verifies how important it is to develop one-
307 dimensional convolutional networks to extract information from the patterns
308 in the sweeps and to make the microalgae classification automatic.

Figure 6: Spectral sweeps from Genesys 10S UV-VIS

309 However, before using these data in the network, a baseline correction was
310 performed in order to remove the exogenous characteristics of the samples.
311 Baseline correction is an important preprocessing technique used to separate
312 true spectroscopic signals from interference effects or to remove background
313 effects, spots, or traces of compounds (Liland et al., 2011). Lineabase cor-
314 rection was performed using the Adaptive iteratively reweighted Penalised
315 Least Squares (airPLS) algorithm, which does not require any user interven-
316 tion or prior information, such as peak detection, etc. The method works by

Figure 7: Spectral sweeps from Genesys 10S UV-VIS labeled

317 iteratively changing the weights of the sum-square errors (SSE) between the
 318 fitted baseline and the original signals, and the weights of the SSE are ob-
 319 tained adaptively using the difference between the previously fitted baseline
 320 and the original signals (Zhang et al., 2010), allowing the processing of new
 321 spectral sweeps automatically.

322 After applying the baseline correction, the sweeps that make up the
 323 Genesys 10S UV-VIS dataset (Figure 7) become those shown in Figure 8,
 324 which shows the patterns of the absorbance peaks present in each of the
 325 genres. Finally, the columns indicating gender was coded using the *One-hot*
 326 technique, which converts each category into a new binary column, assign-
 327 ing the value 1 to the corresponding column if the sample belongs to that
 328 category and 0 otherwise (Potdar et al., 2017).

Figure 8: Spectral sweeps with baseline correction

329 In the research involved in this work, once the data set was obtained, dif-

330 ferent multi-label classification machine learning algorithms were compared
331 to analyze and compare their accuracy. The classification algorithms used in
332 the comparison are SVM, XGBoost, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression,
333 which are widely used in multiclass classification problems. The objective of
334 this analysis is to evaluate the performance of the different algorithms and
335 to establish an initial benchmark, which contributes in the selection of the
336 final algorithm.

337 In order to evaluate the performance of the different algorithms, a cross-
338 validation of the data sets with 10 splits has been performed. This method
339 offers several advantages, as it allows for a more accurate assessment of the
340 true performance of each algorithm by minimizing the impact of any single
341 partition of the dataset. This approach ensures that the performance metrics
342 reflect the algorithms' generalizability to new data, rather than being overly
343 dependent on the specific initial partitioning of the dataset.

344 Once the performance of machine learning algorithms has been analysed,
345 the *Keras* (Chollet et al., 2015) library was used to create the neural network,
346 which allowed the network to be customised by defining the layers and acti-
347 vation functions. A sequential network with 3 convolutional blocks to extract
348 features and a classifier block with 2 dense layers was performed as shown in
349 Figure 9. The first three are 1D convolutional layers, in which *Batch Normal-*
350 *isation* was applied before running the activation function *ReLU* (Rectified
351 Linear Unit), to extract characteristic features from the spectral sweeps. A
352 layer *SpatialDropout1D* was applied between the connections of the convo-
353 lutional layer, while a layer *Flatten* and *Dropout* was applied between the
354 convolutional layer and the dense layer. In the first two dense layers, an
355 activation function *ReLU* was used to interpret the features obtained in the
356 convolutional layers, while the last dense layer includes the activation func-
357 tion *Softmax* to perform multiclass classification. The architecture described
358 has a total of 1,571,621 trainable parameters.

359
360 The neural network model was compiled using the *categorical crossen-*
361 *tropy* loss function, which is widely used in multiclass classification prob-
362 lems. The optimizer used was SGD (*Stochastic Gradient Descent*), which is
363 a popular algorithm in pattern recognition problems, responsible for adjust-
364 ing the weights of the neural network during training (Amari, 1993). The
365 metric used to evaluate model performance was accuracy (*accuracy*), which
366 measures the proportion of correct predictions relative to the total samples.
367 Throughout the network design process, cross-validation was used to evalu-

Figure 9: Neural network architecture

368 ate network performance more thoroughly, thus improving its performance
 369 and avoiding overtuning. The configuration of the cross-validation process,
 370 as in the case of the evaluation of the different machine learning algorithms,
 371 was 10 partitions and several tests were performed by modifying the size of
 372 the filters and kernel of the convolutional network, as well as the size of the
 373 dense output layer in search of the best performance.

374 The neural network model was compiled using the *categorical_crossentropy*
 375 loss function, which is widely used in multiclass classification problems. The
 376 optimizer used was SGD (*Stochastic Gradient Descent*), which is a popu-
 377 lar algorithm in pattern recognition problems, responsible for adjusting the
 378 weights of the neural network during training ([ichi Amari, 1993](#)). The metric
 379 used to evaluate model performance was accuracy (*accuracy*), which mea-
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 381 Throughout the network design process, cross-validation was used to evalu-
 382 ate network performance more thoroughly, thus improving its performance
 383 and avoiding overtuning. The configuration of the cross-validation process,
 384 as in the case of the evaluation of the different machine learning algorithms,
 385 was 10 partitions and several tests were performed by modifying the size of
 386 the filters and kernel of the convolutional network, as well as the size of the
 387 dense output layer in search of the best performance.

388
 389 The results obtained in each of the algorithms used have been tabulated
 390 in Table 1 using the average and standard deviation obtained in all the
 391 cross-validation partitions, providing a more reliable measure of the accuracy
 392 and robustness. The table shows that the 1D convolutional network has
 393 the best classification result of all the algorithms used (98.0%), followed by
 394 Random Forest and XGBoost (96.2% and 95.4%, respectively). These three

395 models have low variability, indicating accurate and consistent models for
 396 the classification task. In contrast, SVM and Logistic Regression show lower
 397 accuracy and higher variability, evidencing less robust performance for this
 398 type of work. In addition, the 1D convolutional network was the one that
 399 best performed the multiclassification task. The architecture of the network
 400 itself has provided the possibility of making use of the Softmax layer to
 401 detect the presence of contamination in the samples analysed, thus making
 402 this model the most suitable for addressing the problem. Notice that the
 403 other algorithms do not include this feature.

Model	Mean Accuracy (%)
1D CNN	98.0 \pm 1.8
Random Forest	96.2 \pm 1.6
XGBoost	95.4 \pm 0.9
SVM	79.1 \pm 3.6
Logistic Regression	75.9 \pm 2.4

Table 1: Classification algorithms used sorted by accuracy

404 Finally, the dataset was divided into training, validation, and test (50/10/40).
 405 The model was trained for 200 epochs with a batch size of 32. During
 406 training, both loss and accuracy were monitored in the training and vali-
 407 dation sets. An evaluation of the validation set was performed every epoch
 408 to monitor how the model was generalising to unseen data. In addition, a
 409 *EarlyStopping* callback with a patience of 5 was used. This allowed train-
 410 ing to be stopped prematurely if no significant improvements in validation
 411 set loss were observed, thereby preventing overfitting and ensuring effective
 412 model training. The network took approximately 1 minute for the entire
 413 training process on a computer equipped with *AMD Ryzen 9 5900HX* and
 414 32 Gb RAM DDR4.

415 During testing, it was observed that the network managed to correctly
 416 classify all samples in the test data set as shown in the confusion matrix
 417 (Figure 10). These results demonstrate that the neural network effectively
 418 learned to recognize and distinguish the relevant features in the spectral
 419 sweeps, and was able to perform accurate classification of genres from pure
 420 laboratory-grown samples.

421 In addition to using the confusion matrix to evaluate the performance of
 422 the multiclass classification network, the F1 score metric has been used and
 423 can be seen in Table 2. The table shows that the model achieves an F1-score

	Validation Score				
	Blank	Chlorella	Scenedesmus	Spirulina	Synechococcus
F1 Score	100 %	97.81 %	100 %	98.21 %	97.2 %

Table 2: Validation score

424 of over 97% across all genus, with a standard deviation of just 1.15%. This
 425 indicates that the model is not only highly accurate, but also consistently bal-
 426 anced in its performance across categories. This stability and precision in the
 427 results suggest a good ability of the model to generalise and classify reliably.
 428 The F1 score metric is the harmonic mean of accuracy and recall, providing a
 429 balanced measure of the model’s ability to correctly identify classes (Goutte
 430 and Gaussier, 2005). This metric is especially useful in multiclass networks
 431 where classes may be unbalanced, as it considers both false positives and
 432 false negatives, providing a more complete view of the model’s performance.
 433 Using the F1 score can provide a more robust and reliable assessment of the
 434 model, especially when accuracy and exhaustiveness are equally important.
 435 The results in Table (Goutte and Gaussier, 2005) corroborate the valida-
 436 tion presented in the confusion matrix (Figure 10), which shows that after
 437 classifying 265 spectral sweeps of samples not previously seen by the neural
 438 network, it has given misclassifications in only 4 of them.

439 3.2. Trials on pilot scale

440 After obtaining the model based on the proposed neural network, dif-
 441 ferent tests were carried out at the IFAPA research centre. Firstly, a small
 442 indoor raceway of 0.56 m² (Figure 1) described in the previous section 2.2
 443 was used. This reactor was inoculated with 5 litres of *Scenedesmus* obtained
 444 from the laboratory and 45 litres of freshwater were added to complete the
 445 usual operating volume of the reactor of 50 litres. The objective of this test
 446 is to verify the correct performance of the network with cultures outside the
 447 laboratory and in different stages of growth, this raceway being the most
 448 suitable for a first test due to the fact that its operating variables are totally
 449 controlled and in indoor conditions. The test was considered to take two
 450 weeks, covering the different stages of culture growth until the steady-state
 451 stage was achieved. A total of 26 spectral sweeps were obtained, again keep-
 452 ing the absorbance values between 0.2 and 1, with the necessary dilutions
 453 depending on the concentration of the culture (see Figure 11). The culture
 454 was inspected using the optical microscope described in Section 2.4 to verify

Figure 10: Confusion matrix

455 that the culture did not present clearly detectable contaminants. As shown
 456 in Figure 12, it was a non-contaminated culture, with only *Scenedesmus*.

457 Spectral sweeps were used as input to the trained convolutional network
 458 after baseline correction and an accuracy of 100% was obtained, the output
 459 of the genus *Scenedesmus* having the highest percentage in all input samples.
 460 It is important to note that the softmax layer output in all samples yielded
 461 a probability greater than 99%, indicating a clear confidence in *Scenedesmus*
 462 detection, as shown in the Table 3, regardless of the stage of growth of the
 463 culture.

464 Once the performance of the convolutional classification network was ver-
 465 ified, the robustness of the convolutional network was tested by introducing

Figure 11: Spectral sweeps from culture of 0.56 m^2 raceway

Figure 12: Photo of the 0.56 m^2 raceway culture obtained on Leica DM500.

466 non-laboratory cultures into the network. For this purpose, in the first in-
 467 stance, sweeps were introduced into the network extracted from the 2600
 468 litre tubular reactor described in Section 2.2. This reactor was inoculated
 469 months before this test with *Scenedesmus*. The culture was analysed again
 470 under the microscope and it was verified that the culture appeared to be free
 471 of contaminants as shown in Figure 13.

472 In this case, a total of six spectral sweeps were taken in a time window
 473 of 2 weeks. As shown in Figure 14, a dilution of the samples was performed
 474 again to keep it in the appropriate absorbance range and then a baseline
 475 correction was applied. After introducing them into the network, the results
 476 obtained in the softmax layer of the network are shown in Table 4. It can
 477 be seen that the classification network indicates that the introduced samples

Softmax Output [%]				
Blank	Chlorella	Scenedesmus	Spirulina	Synechococcus
0.000	0.002	99.998	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.011	99.989	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.003	99.997	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.013	99.986	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.028	99.972	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.007	99.993	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.019	99.980	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.002	99.998	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.002	99.998	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.001	99.999	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.002	99.998	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.001	99.999	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.016	99.984	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.000	100.000	0.000	0.000
0.002	0.277	99.719	0.002	0.001
0.000	0.464	99.534	0.002	0.000
0.000	0.577	99.420	0.002	0.000
0.000	0.778	99.219	0.003	0.000
0.001	0.146	99.851	0.002	0.000
0.001	0.596	99.400	0.003	0.001

Table 3: Softmax output of spectral sweeps of samples from 0.56 m² raceway reactor

478 correspond to the *Scenedesmus* genus with a high percentage, as the rest
 479 of the genera in the softmax layer were less than 1%, indicating that the
 480 network considers the high purity of the culture.

481 After verifying the performance of the convolutional classification net-
 482 work in larger reactors and with nonlaboratory cultures, we proceeded to
 483 use semi-industrial scale raceway reactors located inside a greenhouse, which
 484 have also been previously described in Section 2.2. This validation is an
 485 important trial for the convolutional network because the reactors located
 486 in the greenhouse are subject to a higher degree of contamination than the
 487 reactors used previously. Therefore, the culture introduced into the network
 488 may contain a heterogeneous composition. In this case, 8 spectral sweeps

Figure 13: Photo of the 2.6 m^3 tubular reactor culture obtained on Leica DM500

Figure 14: Spectral sweeps from culture of 2.6 m^3 tubular reactor

489 have been performed on the raceway culture at a time frame of 2 weeks, di-
 490 luting the sample in case the upper limit of absorbance exceeds and applying
 491 lineabase correction to be introduced in the classification network as shown
 492 in Figure 15.

493

494 The results obtained in the softmax output layer of the classification
 495 network in this test show that the network not only detects *Spirulina* clearly,
 496 but in all sweeps the output corresponding to *Chlorella* is also excited, as

Softmax Output [%]				
Blank	Chlorella	Scenedesmus	Spirulina	Synechococcus
0.000	0.001	99.999	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.001	99.999	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.002	99.998	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.056	99.944	0.000	0.000
0.000	0.948	99.049	0.002	0.000
0.000	0.564	99.434	0.001	0.000

Table 4: Softmax output of spectral sweeps of samples from 2.6 m^3 tubular reactor

Figure 15: Spectral sweeps from culture of 80 m^2 raceway reactor

Softmax Output [%]				
Blank	Chlorella	Scenedesmus	Spirulina	Synechococcus
0.006	8.223	0.026	91.403	0.341
0.002	2.833	0.000	97.121	0.045
0.002	3.361	0.001	96.532	0.104
0.011	0.730	0.002	98.935	0.322
0.016	4.218	0.009	95.717	0.041
0.001	4.236	0.000	95.650	0.113
0.004	2.566	0.002	97.389	0.039
0.001	1.187	0.001	98.649	0.161

Table 5: Softmax output of spectral sweeps of samples from 80 m^2 raceway reactor

497 shown in Table 5. This event indicates that the culture may be contaminated
 498 with *Chlorella*. To verify this result, microscope photos were taken, and as
 499 shown in Figure 16, the culture not only contains *Spirulina* cells, but also

500 some *Chlorella* cells.

Figure 16: Photo of the 80 m^2 raceway culture obtained on Leica DM500.

501 Thus, in accordance with the high accuracy of the previous results, the
502 proposed model is presented as a robust and suitable tool for contamination
503 detection in microalgae-based production systems. The current limitations
504 of the current version of model are the small variety of genera used in the
505 dataset and the necessity to validate it under more environmental conditions.

506 4. Conclusions and future works

507 In conclusion, the classification neural network has obtained highly sat-
508 isfactory results. The results obtained in the validation carried out with
509 samples from real reactors from the IFAPA research facilities have shown a
510 correct functioning of the classification network, with a 100% accuracy rate.
511 However, the most outstanding feature of this validation stage has been the
512 capacity to detect contamination in the culture by analysing the *softmax*
513 output layer and placing a threshold on it to indicate whether the culture
514 has any type of contamination. This approach enables efficient culture mon-
515 itoring without the need for additional investment in new acquisition equip-
516 ment or the allocation of qualified personnel for optical microscopy or flow
517 cytometer. Furthermore, it plays a significant role in maintaining stable reac-
518 tor operations by allowing early detection of potential contaminants. Notice

519 that when high level of contaminants are detected, the production must be
520 stopped to reinoculate the system, thus affecting the production costs.

521 The work has been done completely in Python, and since the network is
522 already trained, its execution only requires selecting the .csv files containing
523 the spectral sweeps and running it. The script automatically applies the
524 baseline correction and entering the resulting values in the network, obtaining
525 as a response the output of the softmax layer and the name of the genus with
526 the highest probability.

527 Two main areas for future work are identified. The first is the expansion
528 of the dataset size in both number of samples and detectable genera,
529 which will allow the tool to classify with greater capacity for generalisation
530 and in turn detect a larger range of cultures and identify a wider variety of
531 contaminants. The second is to improve the interpretation of the softmax
532 layer to improve contaminant detection, along with statistical analysis of the
533 results across multiple spectral sweeps. Since spectrophotometer scans of
534 the same sample are not identical, the percentage output of possible con-
535 taminants may vary. To overcome this problem, developing a tool that takes
536 input from multiple spectral scans of the same culture and applies statistical
537 analysis techniques to the softmax results of each scan can be key to improv-
538 ing the robustness of the contamination detection capability. Producing a
539 more reliable contaminant detection result.

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